

D7.3 Dissemination & Communication Report

Final v1.0

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Abstract

In this document we present the evolution of the Dissemination and Communication Plan designed to disseminate and communicate DAFNE+ project, the social media communication strategy, and the user engagement strategy for each use case along the first 18 months of the project. Also, the challenges that we have encountered and the next steps we have ahead of us.

Keywords

Dissemination, Communication, Social networks, user engagement strategy, social media strategy.

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Abbreviations

KPI	key performance indicator
NFT	Non Fungible Token
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
EU	European Union
ERC	Ethereum Request for Comment
ISCC	International Standard Content Code

Executive summary

The activities of dissemination and communication of DAFNE+ have been focused on the creation of awareness about the project, the blockchain technology and DAFNE+'s value proposition for the creative and artistic communities.

In this sense, the communication actions have paid close attention to the need to educate these communities about something as new and incipient as blockchain technology and its applications to different sectors that are not specifically technological.

To achieve this, we have concentrated on the written content through educational posts that aim to explain certain contents and terms related to the project's main target audience. These posts have been published regularly to obtain impact on the project's blog but also trying to grow an educated community around it.

These publications have been shared across social media. We have focused our efforts in two main social networks, such as LinkedIn and X. In these first 18 months of the project, we have concentrated on creating the visual identity of the project and generating a community. We are now reaching 100 followers in X and more than 50 followers in LinkedIn. Altogether they count 150 followers which goes beyond our KPI for the first year situated in 100.

On the other hand, we have also created video content, that we have published in the project's YouTube channel. For the moment, five videos have been uploaded, one with the academic explanation of the project and another one with some promotional content. In addition, three videos with interviews to each Use Case have been produced. The purpose of the audiovisual content created was to aid the events and webinars that we aim to attend throughout the project. In YouTube channel we have six subscribers.

In addition to this, we are focusing on two lines of communication, one general of the project and another one more detailed about the three use cases that have been designed at the beginning of the project. The three use cases have specific artistic communities that will have their own line of communication strategy. Those communities are going to be the testers of the platform.

In the near future there will also be some special promotional material concerning the platform launch such as a Press Release and social media content and a blog post. Once DAFNE+ platform is launched some specific content will be created to help new users with the onboarding process of using the platform.

Introduction

Purpose and Scope

The main purpose of the communication and dissemination strategy of DAFNE+ project is to attract attention to the project and the platform. Also these activities aim to create a community of future users that will benefit from the business model of the platform and may serve as proof of the platform's usefulness.

Dissemination and Communication Strategy

Performance Review

The Communication Strategy that has been designed for the project works in three main aspects:

- **General:** Educational information concerning some aspects of the blockchain technology, special terminology, and the purpose of the project specifically.
- **Events and project promotion:** Material concerning the different milestones that the project is getting to and the partners that take part in it. Also, news pieces concerning General Meetings, webinars, events and the different stages of the construction of the platform.
- **Specific and tailored content:** each use case has its own community behind, strong groups of potential users that will need some specific content and material addressed to them. Also, once the platform is launched, some helpful informative material that will allow the users to get the most out of the platform.

Dissemination and Communication activities implemented

Visual Identity

Logo and brand assets

The logo and the brand materials have been designed. The color palette has been defined and the norms in which the primary and secondary colors need to be used are also determined. You can see the final outcome a document on the SharePoint of the project.

Official templates

Once we had designed all the brand colors and typographies, we proceeded to create the templates of all documentation that will be needed along the project such as the slides master or the deliverables. Both documents are essential for the normal development of the project, not only for attending the meeting and showing the work progress of each work package, but for communicating the results of the research and conveying all relevant information for DAFNE+. This information is also available on the SharePoint of the project.

Online Channels

Project website

The official project website <https://dafneplus.eu/> is already running. It has three main pages: home, news and contact.

- **Home:** Here you can find the general explanation of the project, the partners that take part in it and the expert counselors that are mentoring the project.
- **News:** In this section of the webpage is where we are addressing content to our audience. Not only the milestones that the project gets to accomplish but the different informative content that we are sharing. We have been publishing at a regular interval of every two weeks, resulting in twenty-six published posts as of M18.
- **Contact:** a contact application form is issued to receive contacts.

Social media

As of our social media channels we have achieved our KPIs for the first year (M12), that was situated in a hundred followers across all platforms. We had a hundred and twenty-two followers at M12.

DAFNE+ Social Networks	
Followers	Year 1
X (former Twitter)	76
LinkedIn	45
YouTube	1
Posts on Social Networks	Year 1
X (former Twitter)	43
LinkedIn	9

TABLE 1 TOTAL SUBSCRIBERS AND POSTS ON EACH SOCIAL NETWORK AS FOR THE 1ST YEAR (JUN 2023)

In this sense these are the ciphers we have in December 2023, as of M18.

- X had one hundred and four followers as of 18/12/2023

FIGURE 1 SCREENSHOT OF X ACCOUNT DETAILS

- We have 6 subscribers and 3 videos in **YouTube** as of 18/12/2023. (other 2 videos not published yet)

FIGURE 2 YOUTUBE CHANNEL 18/12/2023

Use Cases

Several meetings have been celebrated to understand the purpose of each use case and the value proposition for their communities, as the target audience that we are addressing. A video interview has been recorded in M15 in order to explain each use case. The results will be published altogether with a written post before the platform launch, in M18.

In addition, the consortium partner responsible for each use case has disseminated independently content about the project in its social networks.

UC1

Use Case 1 is centered in Cultural heritage, so it refers to the totality of elements, traditions, beliefs, values, and customs that are inherited from past generations, preserved in the present, and passed on to future generations. It encompasses both tangible and intangible aspects of human civilization and that is a vital part of a society's identity.

To define this Use Case we are planning to visit a Tourism Fair in January that promotes Spanish Cultural Heritage but also other cultures and nationalities.

In the first phase of testing, Manchester Metropolitan University will run a one-week [Creative Jam](#) in January 2024 with their students and the ones from the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC) in Barcelona. They will be introduced to the fairer business models and working practices made possible by the project such as allowing collaborative authorship to be acknowledged and remunerated using innovative NFT technology and legal schemes.

Also during the 4th General Meeting that took place in Paris in September 2023 we recorded an interview about UC1.

<https://youtu.be/aZa3EA6OMrq?si=gKxIPjF8MNkYIFU->

UC2

Concerning Use case 2, IRCAM, has published some specific content to drive attention to this institution. Specifically, two written contents that were published in DAFNE+ blog before M15. One explaining how a music can also be turned into an NFT and how this can be an opportunity for musicians and sound engineers, and the other one introducing IRCAM institution as partner of DAFNE+.

[Music as an NFT](#)

[IRCAM's partner presentation](#)

Also during the 4th General Meeting that took place in Paris in September 2023 we recorded an interview about UC2.

UC3

Fab Lab Barcelona and IAAC have published several posts regarding DAFNE+ project along these months. In total, IAAC has prepared 5 pieces of content that were meant to be distributed further on M15. They use Instagram (4 pieces) as main social network, and LinkedIn (1 post). All tried to explain and present DAFNE+ project.

[Blog Post on Distributed Design Platform, 18th July, 2023](#)

[LinkedIn post 15 October, 2023](#)

[Instagram post 9th October, 2023](#)

Nevertheless, during the 4th General Meeting that took place in Paris in September 2023 we recorded an interview about UC3.

Events, Conferences and webinars

Events

Cultural and Creative Industries (Barcelona, July 2023)

The Cultural and creative industries event in Barcelona that took place in July 2023 was an excellent opportunity for DAFNE+ to explain the project to a broader and specialised audience. Besides the post that was published in the blog and several posts in social networks about the event, some promotional content was created. Specifically, a video that helped the presentation at the event.

[DAFNE+ explains the project in Barcelona](#)

URL-based sharing technology demos

DAFNE+ has been researching alternative decentralized technologies for sharing and collaborating based on creations that contain their content embedded in the URL. These developments have been formally introduced in these events:

- ScrawlLink extension: at from Scratch session of the 5th VIU (Barcelona annual live coding meeting) (April 27, Barcelona).
- FromScrawl: at Live Coders Event of the Algorithmic Pattern Salon (Barcelona, 25 Nov 2023)

And informally shown in Sync 2023 (Festival de Musica Electrónica de Carabanchel, Madrid, 22 de Abril de 2023); and Creative Code Hideout (Berlin, August 20, 2023), “Show ur your Screens” (Berlin, August 24 2023), and Livecodera Berlin (Berlin, Sept 3 2023)

MMU Webinar on DAFNE+

Also the School of Digital Arts (MMU) celebrated a webinar [explaining the project on November, 15th](#).

Workshops and Webinars

DAFNE+ organized participatory workshops on fair economic models that informed the design of our revenue models. These events helped introducing DAFNE+ project to the Use Case communities and have a direct co-design experience with their communities. The first took place in IRCAM Forum (Paris, 29-31 2023), while the second took place in FabLab Barcelona (Barcelona, 16 May 2023).

Promotional materials

Videos

A video was created to help explain the project when the project leader attended a webinar or event in which DAFNE+ project could be exposed, like the one mentioned in July, 2023. It is published in the Youtube channel and it has 19 views.

FIGURE 3 VIDEOS UPLOADED TO DAFNE+ YOUTUBE CHANNEL.

As explained above, we have recorded another three pieces of video content. They are interviews to each Use Case partner. These pieces of content will help explain the project and also will be used in the future to complete a whole video with other relevant content such as technical aspects of the platform or an interview to the project leader. The interviews were published in M18.

Publications

Conferences

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101061548

1) T. Chatzis, D. Konstantinidis and K. Dimitropoulos, "3D Pose Estimation Using a Global and Local Cross-Attention Mechanism," in IEEE International Conference on Imaging Systems and Techniques, pp. 1-6, October 17-19, 2023, Copenhagen, Denmark.

2) Tenorio Fornés, Ámbar, Olivia Jack, and Felix Roos. 2023. "Synthesthesia: Sharing Patterns for a Choreographic Audio and Visual Live Coding Experience." In Algorithmic Pattern Salon. Then Try This. <https://doi.org/10.21428/108765d1.3c0227a0>.

Journals

1) D. Konstantinidis, I. Papastratis, K. Dimitropoulos and P. Daras, "Multi-Manifold Attention for Vision Transformers," in *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 123433-123444, 2023, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3329952.

Engagement strategy

Surveys and consultations

At the beginning of the project a Survey was conducted to gather information about user willingness to use our platform. Several events occurred across various countries, engaging diverse audiences to understand their needs and gather user requirements. The consortium's use case partners spearheaded the initiative, driving the completion of questionnaires by 82 potential users. This endeavor not only validated the consortium's beliefs but also provided a tangible foundation for understanding the specific needs of the users. This survey was mainly conducted by the technical partners in "*D2.1 User Requirements and DAFNE+ architecture*".

[Introducing the Dafneplus Survey](#)

Networking opportunities

Several appointments have been made to create networking opportunities such as The [Cultural and Creative Industries event in Barcelona](#), during the Spanish Presidency of the EU. At that venue DAFNE+ had the opportunity to explain the project.

Also the webinar we celebrated in October with the community of artists gathered in the Glitch3 event celebrated in Paris. We obtained very good feedback from the audience and they were all willing to try the platform once it was launched.

[DAFNE+ Webinar at Glitch3](#)

Standardisation Activities

Overview

In the first half of the project lifetime, DAFNE+ consortium has carried out a survey of the blockchain relevant standardisation and explored their value to DAFNE+ with respect to: standardisation/ initiatives that DAFNE+ can affect and standardisation/initiatives that DAFNE+ platform has to adopt/respect. The results of our work are shown in the following table.

Our next steps that will be taken in the 2nd half of the project lifetime is to refine this list so that DAFNE+ contributes to a subset of these initiatives. With respect to adoption, details are provided in the deliverables of WP4 (for example, DAFNE+ has adopted ERC 1155 tokens).

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Standardisation Body	Working Group	Standardisation Activity	Description	Category	Status	URL	Value to DAFNE+
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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101061548

1	ISO/TC 307	WG 2: Security, privacy and identity	ISO/CD 24138	<p>This document specifies the syntax and structure of the International Standard Content Code (ISCC), as an identification system for digital assets (including encodings of text, images, audio, video or other content across all media-sectors). It also describes ISCC metadata and the use of ISCC in conjunction with other schemes, such as the schemes defined by ISO/TC 46/SC 9. An ISCC applies to a specific digital asset and is a data-descriptor constructed from multiple hashes using the algorithms and rules in this document. Organisations, individuals and machines may generate ISCCs for numerous kinds of digital assets and use them for identification and management of those assets. The generation or use of an ISCC in itself does not make any statement or claim about authorship or ownership of the identified content.</p>	Digital Assets	Under Development	https://www.iso.org/standard/77899.html	<p>The main distinguishing feature of the ISCC to other existing standardised content identifiers (e.g., ISBN, DOI, or ISRC) is the fact that the ISCC is generated from the content file itself. This means that an ISCC can be generated by anyone with access to the digital media asset, free of charge by using open-source software, without the need to exchange any external metadata beforehand. By using ISCC, anyone with access to digital content – it could be the original creator, a publisher, an intermediary, an online platform or a consumer – can decentrally generate the same (or similar) identifier from the same (or similar) digital media asset. This allows anyone to unambiguously identify the same or probabilistically match similar content independent of centralised organisations, registries or proprietary third-party services and software.</p>
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								<p>If ISCC codes are declared on public blockchain networks, creators and rightsholders can associate metadata, rights management information, credentials or other claims to the identifier. Consequently, anyone with access to the media asset will be able to reverse-lookup all information that may be associated with the identifier.</p> <p>ISCC codes are designed to be used in decentralised media environments and the web3. Decentralised content-derived identifiers support many use cases that do not require the use of blockchain networks. In this sense, ISCC codes are perfectly suited to bridge the shift of paradigm from web2 to web3, which we can observe in the media industries and elsewhere.</p>
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2	ISO/T C 307	WG 1: Fou ndat ions	ISO 22739: 2020	This document provides fundamental terminology for blockchain and distributed ledger technologies.	Blockchai n Vocabular y	New version under development	https:// www .iso.or g/sta ndard /7377 1.html	This document will provide a useful guide to use the appropriate terminology when describing blockchain related architectures and functionalities during the development of the project.
3	ISO/T C 307	WG 6: Use case s	ISO/T R 3242	Use cases	Use cases	Under Development	https:// www .iso.or g/sta ndard /7954 3.html	Possible contribution
4	ISO/T C 307	WG 1: Fou ndat ions	ISO 23257: 2022	This document specifies a reference architecture for Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) systems including blockchain systems. The reference architecture addresses concepts, cross-cutting aspects, architectural considerations, and architecture views, including functional	Blockchai n Architect ure	Published	https:// www .iso.or g/sta ndard /7509 3.html	This document covers some important aspects to consider during the development of the project such as: security, identity, privacy, governance, interoperability and various architectural considerations such as the storage, the control and the permissions.

				components, roles, activities, and their relationships for blockchain and DLT.				
5	ISO/TC 307	WG 1: Foundations	ISO/CD TR 6039	Identifiers of subjects and objects for the design of blockchain systems	Blockchain system design	Under Development	https://www.iso.org/standard/81978.html	Possible contribution
6	ISO/TC 307	WG 6: Uses	ISO/WD TR 6277	Data flow model for blockchain and DLT use cases	Blockchain systems data flow	Under Development	https://www.iso.org/standard/82158.html	Possible contribution

7	ISO/TC 307	WG 7: Interoperability	ISO/AWI TS 23516	This document specifies a framework, recommendations and requirements for interoperability between DLT systems, between DLT and entities outside the DLT system, the relationship and interactions between these and cross-cutting aspects.	Interoperability	Under Development	https://www.iso.org/standard/82098.html	Possible contribution
8	ISO/TC 307	WG 2: Security, privacy and identity	ISO/WD TR 23642	Overview of smart contract security good practice and issues	Security	Under Development	https://www.iso.org/standard/81772.html	Possible contribution

9	ISO/TC 307	WG 5: Governance	ISO/TS 23635:2022	<p>This document provides guiding principles and a framework for the governance of DLT systems.</p> <p>The document also provides guidance on the fulfilment of governance, including risk and regulatory contexts, that supports the effective, efficient, and acceptable use of DLT systems.</p>	Governance	Published	https://www.iso.org/standard/76480.html	<p>This document could prove valuable during the development of the DAFNE+ DAO. (Distributed Autonomous Organization)</p>
10	ISO/TC 307	WG 2: Security, privacy and identity	ISO/TR 23244:2020	<p>This document provides an overview of privacy and personally identifiable information (PII) protection as applied to blockchain and distributed ledger technologies (DLT) systems.</p>	Privacy	Published	https://www.iso.org/standard/75061.html	<p>This could act as a guide for the privacy related concerns of the blockchain realm of DAFNE+</p>

1	ISO/T C 307	WG 3: Smart Contract s and thei r appl icati ons	ISO/T R 23455: 2019	This document provides an overview of smart contracts in BC/DLT systems; describing what smart contracts are and how they work. It also discusses methods of interaction between multiple smart contracts. This document focuses on technical aspects of smart contracts. Smart contracts for legally binding use and applications will only be briefly mentioned in this document.	Smart Contracts	Published	https:// www .iso.or g/sta ndard /7562 4.html	This document could provide useful guidelines during the development of the smart contracts of the DAFNE+ project.
1 2	IEEE CTS/B SC - Blockc hain Standards	DBC - Data for mat for Bloc	IEEE 2418.1 0- 2022	A baseline architectural framework will be defined in this standard. In addition, the general process for digital asset management on blockchain will be outlined.	Digital Assets	Published	https:// /stan dards. ieee.o rg/iee e/241 8.10/7 630/	This could help with the management of the digital assets (e.g. NFTs) on DAFNE+.

	Committee	Blockchain Systems						
13	IEEE C/BDL - Blockchain and Distributed Ledgers	DAI - Digital Asset Identification	IEEE 3207-2022	This standard defines the data fields, types, and formats related to digital assets to improve digital asset identification efficiency. Moreover, the definition and description of methods and data structures in this standard provide guidance for blockchain-based digital asset identification.	Digital Assets	Published	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3207/10239/	This could help define unique IDs for the digital assets of DAFNE+.
14	IEEE C/BDL - Blockchain and Distributed	NFD A - Non-Fungible	P3220	This guide describes the processes used in the conversion of physical assets to NFTs, the lifecycle management process of NFT derivatives, and the interaction and display modes of NFTs in the real world. Specifically it includes the generation, issuance, exchange, rights confirmation, system interaction and display process of NFTs.	Digital Assets	Under Development	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/322	Possible contribution

	uted Ledger s	e Digi tal Ass ets_ P32 20					0/106 89/	
1 5	IEEE C/BDL - Blockc hain and Distrib uted Ledger s	ICC - Inte rope rabil ity Cros s Chai n	P3204	The standard describes the process of distributed cross-chain transaction consistency protocols to enhance the interoperability between Blockchain networks. This standard also describes terminologies, data modeling, key indicators, commit and rollback mechanisms, and other mechanisms needed for the implementation of cross-chain transaction consistency without a centralized third-party.	Interoper ability	Under Development	https:// /stan dards. ieee.o rg/iee e/320 4/102 35/	Possible contribution

1 6	IEEE C/BDL - Blockchain and Distributed Ledgers	DAE - Digital Asset Exchange	P3208	This standard defines an exchange model for blockchain-based digital assets. The exchange model includes operational processes, data security and information security requirements, and transaction rules. The standard also defines the general technical requirements of the exchange model and describes the entity functions in the exchange model.	Digital Assets	Under Development	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3208/40/	Could be useful for the NFT marketplace processes of DAFNE+
1 7	IEEE C/BDL - Blockchain and Distributed Ledgers	DAC - Digital Asset Classification	P3206	This standard defines and classifies blockchain-based digital assets and different types thereof. Furthermore, the standard specifies terms used with blockchain-based digital assets.	Digital Assets	Under Development	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3206/10238/	This could be useful in order to classify the different digital assets listed and created on DAFNE+

18	IEEE C/BDL - Blockchain and Distributed Ledgers	IDA C - Interoperability Data Authentication and Communication	P3205	<p>Blockchain interoperability is the ability of two or more blockchain systems or applications to exchange information and to mutually use the information that has been exchanged. There are diverse cross-chain use cases and differentiated cross-platform bridging solutions that are difficult to reuse. There are many disadvantages in existing solutions, such as applicability, security, scalability, and performance. These make them difficult to apply to diverse blockchain, cross-chain scenarios and future applications. The interfaces and protocols play a very important role in realizing interoperability. Therefore, the standard of cross-chain interoperability interfaces and protocols, especially those for data authentication and communication among homogeneous and heterogeneous blockchains systems is needed. Such protocols coordinate blockchains while supporting multiple cross-chain models and levels to meet business demands without the need to customize gateways or exchanges for specific use</p>	Interoperability	Published Draft	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3205/10237/	This could help with the possible interoperability functions implemented in DAFNE+
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cases. The standard provides an infrastructure of cross chain interoperability, as well as interfaces and protocols of data authentication and communication for homogeneous and heterogeneous blockchain interoperability. The protocols include the distributed identity protocol, metadata protocol, on-chain proof conversion protocol, and cross-chain communication protocol.

19	IEEE C/BDL - Blockchain and Distributed Ledgers	DCS WG - Digital Collection Services	P3221	This standard defines technical requirements of a digital collection service based on blockchain technologies. A technical architecture, functional components, and security requirements are defined.	Digital Collection	Under Development	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3221/10924/	Possible contribution
20	IEEE C/BDL - Blockchain and Distributed Ledgers	BT - Blockchain Testing	P3214	This standard defines definitions, types, test specifications, test methods and test processes for blockchain systems. Test contents are included for each type of test. This standard also defines the test architecture of blockchain systems, including but not limited to functional testing, performance testing, security testing, stability testing, and compliance testing.	Testing	Under Development	https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/3214/10244/	Valuable for the development of the Blockchain infrastructure and services

20	IRTF	DINRG		Decentralized Internet Infrastructure research group	Blockchain		https://datatracker.ietf.org/rq/about/	Possible contribution
21	INATBA	Standards committee		International Association for Trusted Blockchain Applications	Blockchain		https://inatba.org/	Possible contribution

TABLE 2 STANDARDISATION BODIES

Conclusions

A summary of the activities of this WP can be found in the following table:

KPIs for dissemination & communication	Year 1	Now
Members of the Dafneplus ecosystem	100	200
Workshops for needs' extraction in the phase of co-creation	3	4
Events (incl. scientific conferences and business events) Dafneplus is (re)presented	4	5
Press releases delivered to traditional media	1	Sept'2023
Website unique visitors (based on Google Analytics)	300	1000
References of Dafneplus on other Websites	3	3
Followers in social networks	100	145
Posts in social networks	25	76
Number of scientific publications in peer-reviewed publications	2	0
Number of webinars/tutorials	1	1
Number of special sessions/workshops co-located at international conferences/EU events	5	0
Number of competitions/events		

Number of events organized for decision and policy makers incl. the final event.		
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TABLE 3 SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

At this point in the project, we have met the objectives set and we have been able to see how well the project has been received by our target audience. Soon, we will open a new stage after the launch of the platform that will allow us to validate our hypotheses.

Next steps will be recollecting feedback of the users to improve the platform at the same time that we increase our community of users.

